

Modeling groundwater flow in upper Seonath basin, Chhattisgarh, India

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ABSTRACT

Groundwater is one of the major available fresh water in our country. Due to its over exploitation, fulfilling the demands for domestic, agricultural and industrial purpose, groundwater level is falling very rapidly day by day especially during summer season in arid and semi-arid regions, leading to water scarcity problems. The present paper covers study and analysis of groundwater flow in Upper Seonathbasin, a sub basin of Mahanadi river in Chhattisgarh by developing a groundwater flow model. Study area extend from 20°16'N to 22°41'N latitude 80°25'E to 82°35'E longitude comprises of two district of Chhattisgarh namely Durg and Rajnandgaon having a total geographical spread of 7292 sq.km. From the field observation it was found that there is a considerable rate of change in water table, especially during the summer season in the past years. This fluctuation in water table is generally caused due to land use/land cover change, over exploitation in unscientific manner. Therefore it becomes necessary to study the groundwater before its exploitation so that a proper balance is maintained between the recharge and extraction. In this study Groundwater flow simulation model has been developed using Visual MODFLOW package. Simulation results help in fetching information about the hydraulic head, drawdown, flow direction etc. The graphs and maps generated using the Visual MODFLOW tool helps us in predicting the groundwater flow condition.

Key words : Groundwater Model, MODFLOW, Upper SeonathBasin, Ground water flow, GIS

Introduction

Groundwater is a major source of fresh water and is an important part of hydrological cycle. Freshwater resources are critically important in economy, biologically and ecologically. Water is essential requirement for all living organisms. For any country water plays very important role in his social economic and cultural progress. The demand of water is increasing in earth for sustaining life and environments one good thing is that water is a natural renewable resources. Therefore, the proper management re-

quired for protection of natural resources. Groundwater models are very useful for managing the water for upcoming demands. Groundwater modelling is a scientific tool for study and analysis the complex system. There are many types for preparing the groundwater models for any system, among them the best is Numerical modelling which provides accurate and real-time prediction of groundwater resources (Koohestani *et al.*, 2013).

Numerical Model: A computer model, using finite difference, finite element or other method, with an approximate solution of the governing flow and/

or transport equations. Numerical models are typically used to represent more complex systems. A numerical model uses numerical methods to solve the governing equations of groundwater flow and/or contaminant transport. Visual MODFLOW is a modular three dimensional finite difference based groundwater simulation system. It is primarily written by United States Geological Survey (1988) (McDonald and Harbaugh, 2003; Harbaugh *et al.*, 2000). The model is capable of modelling time-dependent flow as well as heat and mass transport problems (Kumar, 2002). Several similar studies have been investigated to perform groundwater modelling in Upper Seonathbasin are:

Tripathi *et al.*, (2009) conducted a study for groundwater assessment of a small watershed using Visual MODFLOW. The analysis was performed to know the impact of different flow and contaminant properties on hydraulic head, dispersion and chemical reaction in small groundwater basin. He had been performed for the Kurdihnal watershed adjoining the Patan block of Durg district in Chhattisgarh (Palanisami *et al.*, 2005; Thiyagarajan and Ranghaswami, 2003) have made an attempt to estimate the amount of groundwater for the Gunder river basin, using Visual MODFLOW. The model, when applied to the study area, shows the permissible error of ± 10 to 20%. For better modelling results the error should be minimized. The results showed that the flow direction was more or less coincided with the general slope and there was an inflow and outflow across to western and eastern boundaries. Shah *et al.*, (2010) have also conducted a study on assessment and management of groundwater in Upper Mahanadi Basin using same modelling technique. Sekhar *et al.*, (2006) has adopted an integrated groundwater modelling approach for better assessment of water balance components. The model study shows that impact of pumping results in regional ground water flows influencing the hydro-geologic regime in the recharge zone of the sub basin. MODFLOW is calibrated assuming specified transmissivity for each of the zones obtained from several pump tests in the region (Youssef and GAD MI, 2012).

Due to the fluctuation in the availability of groundwater level in pre monsoon and post monsoon in Upper Seonathbasin, therefore the purpose of this study is assessment of groundwater that will permit the appropriate tools and techniques for interdisciplinary prospects to enhanced management

of groundwater condition and water resources systems during pre-monsoon and post monsoon periods to be systematically evaluated with existing information for Upper Seonathsub basin. The main objectives of study are, a steady state groundwater flow simulation using Visual MODFLOW software and its calibration, provide an over view of groundwater occurrences of Seonathbasin in different season and assessment of the exiting groundwater resources of the Seonathbasin for effective planning and management.

Materials and Methods

Study Area Characterization

The study area focused is Upper Seonathsub-basin which is sub basin of Mahanadi basin and it is located at upstream of Durg, the two districts of Chhattisgarh State namely Durg and Rajnandgaon are covered in this basin (Ahmad *et al.*, 2015). Location of study area 20'16"N to 22'41"N latitude 80'25"E to 82'35"E longitude the catchment area this basin cover two district which include 13 blocks 6 from Durg district and 7 from Rajnandgaon district, and the total study area 7292 sq.km. The Seonath river basin is originated from two rivers i.e. Kharkhara river and Tandula river and divided into 16 catchments. The area selected for the study is the Upper Seonathsub-basin and is situated inside the Seonath basin of well-known Mahanadi river basin in Chhattisgarh. Entire study area of Upper Seonath sub-basin falls within the state of Chhattisgarh. The mean annual rainfall in the basin varies from 1005 mm to 1255 mm.

Climate region under consideration is characterized by general dryness, excluding during southwest rainy season Rajput *et al.*, (2014). The hot season is from March to May. The southwest monsoon generally sets in over this region during the second week of June and rainfall activity continuous till second week of October. The second half of October and entire month of November constitutes the post monsoon season.

Total geographical area of Upper Seonathsub basin is 7292 sq.km out of which agricultural land occupies about 62.16% of total geographical area, built up area occupies 3.92% of total area, forest occupies 20.14% of total area, and Tree clad occupies 3.60% of total area which has minimum area in Upper Seonathsub basin, waste land occupies 6.47% of to-

Fig. 1. Location map of Upper Seonath basin

Fig. 2. Site selection based on Dynamic Groundwater Resources of Chhattisgarh Board, (2011)

tal area, water bodies occupies is about 3.70% of total geographical area. Thus it can be concluded that agricultural area covers maximum area where as tree clad and water bodies cover very less or minimum area.

Governing equation of groundwater flow modelling

A model that simulates groundwater flow is the simplified representation of the sub surface aquifer system, which may be used to predict aquifer response to various input/output stresses. Groundwater flow in three dimensions in a porous medium of constant density can be expressed by the following partial differential equation (Jangade *et al.*, 2015).

MODFLOW is a modular three dimensional finite difference groundwater model developed by U. S. Geological Survey to simulate saturated flow through a layered porous media (Xu *et al.*, 2009; Koohestani *et al.*, 2013). The Partial Differential Equation solved is for $h(x, y, z, \text{ and } t)$ the governing three dimensional flow equation used by MODFLOW combines Darcy's law and the principal of conservation of mass.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(K_{xx} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(K_{yy} \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K_{zz} \frac{\partial h}{\partial z} \right) - W = S_s \frac{\partial h}{\partial t}$$

Where K_{xx} , K_{yy} , and K_{zz} are hydraulic conductivity along the x , y and z direction, h represents the potential head, W is the volumetric flux per unit volume being pumped, S_s is the specific storage of the porous material and t is time. This equation describes ground-water flow under non-equilibrium conditions in a heterogeneous and anisotropic medium and provided the principal axes of hydraulic conductivity are aligned with the coordinate directions.

The VISUAL MODFLOW software developed by (McDonald and Harbaugh, 2003). In this programmer, using the block centered finite difference approach to solve and approximation to the groundwater flow equation simulates groundwater flow. For groundwater flow modelling various data hydrological metrological and toposheets are collected from respective departments or observed and measured in study area. All toposheets are georeferenced and digitalized, the hydrological behavior of a watershed may be understood by the digital elevation model (DEM), it is based on various information's including elevation/altitude, drainage and basin

boundaries is delineated in GIS. Data preparation for and watershed model can be done using GIS (Baghel *et al.*, 2014). Various other morphological parameter of the watershed such as watershed boundary, drainage map of the Upper Seonathbasin, area of the watershed which is required for the model, were also extracted using digital elevation model. The river, observation wells and pumping wells are also digitized which directly used as a input data for Visual MODFLOW after competitions of input data preparation work for model, import the all required input parameters for model like grid, watershed boundary, location of observation well and river etc. Those inputs are in the form of shape file from GIS or excel sheets are fed to form boundary condition of the model. All observed parameter head, recharge and aquifer property such as hydraulic conductivity, specific yield, total porosity, transmissivity and specific storage are defined in model.

The model is developed to simulate the existing hydrological system and the processes that control the ground water flow. The ground water flow equation with the specification of flow and initial head conditions at the boundaries constitutes a mathematical representation of the aquifer system. Recharge and pumping well has been deliberate for the study area and assigned in model. The observation wells head values and village wise draft value for well has been assigned in the model. The aquifer parameters including hydraulic conductivity [K (m/day)], specific yield (S_y), and specific storage [S (L-1)] were assigned layer wise for each layer (Holzbecher and Sorek, 2005). Boundary conditions evapo-transpiration, recharge, river, constant head were also assigned in the model (Sinha *et al.*, 2016)

Results and Discussion

Simulation and Calibration

Initially the model has been simulated in steady state for period of five year for both pre and post monsoon. All data, such as constant head, recharge, evapo-transpiration have been entered season wise so that transient state run may carried out season wise. In initial simulation the model results as most of the area are dry due to pumping data. Hence it has been corrected by adjusting the values of hydraulic conductivity.

Fig. 3. Velocity vector with recharge for Upper Seonath basin in first and second layer in pre monsoon.

Regional flow pattern of Groundwater

The flow direction and velocity vector obtained for different period indicates (Fig. 3 & 4) that majority of the flow direction is in North East direction. This is route of the groundwater movement from the up-

Fig. 4. Velocity vector with recharge for Upper Seonathbasin in first layer in post monsoon.

per higher altitude to lower altitude. It has been also observed that there is less flow pattern in layer one during pre-monsoon and water table during this season is very low in high built-up areas and they are also controlling the flow patterns. The Fig. 5 shows in Upper Seonath basin the red color contour reveals the drawdown of the study area for first layer, which varies from location to location and block. And the blue color contour shows in the study area map are head equipotential for the value of 331.7745 m. the color shading shows the head equipotential in particular location which minimum

Fig. 5. Drawdown contour and equipotential contour

and maximum values are from 350 m to 366 m. Few heads of the observation sites located near the constant head boundary, i.e. reservoirs and channel has not shown any change with time and equipotential head near this structure shows negative depth, i.e. -20m. maximum equipotential head is 60 m near the high abstract locations. In Fig. 4 post monsoon season result shows shallow water table depth for whole basin and flow direction have no effect due of pumping.

Flow Budget from the model output

Results of flow budget (Fig. 6) indicate that an

Fig. 6. Comparison Graph between Input and Output

Fig. 7. Calibration of model for head in the study area

amount of 1200000 m³ per day has been pumped on the pre monsoon from the constant available effective storage of the aquifer. The recharge from the stream and storage support the inflow of water in the area. Constant head is insufficient for constant abstraction by 20000 m³ per day. The inflow outflow to the system is also balanced till the month of June-July. After start of monsoon, i.e. June- July, situation reversed after increase in recharge to the system. Inspection of drawdown in individual pumping wells indicated influence of the wells is very limited and rarely interfering the other wells.

Model Calibration

The observation well used during model has been implemented for calibration. In model, calculated heads and observed heads have been analyzed and calibrated. Majority of the heads falls in 95 per cent confidence level (Fig. 7). Same simulation has been carried out for pre and post monsoon. The calculated and observed heads have been plotted for all the stress period. It is found that behavior of heads is changing with seasonal change in the water table.

Conclusion

Groundwater resources are very useful and important in sustaining people's lives in Upper Seonathbasin. However, the intensive use of groundwater has reduces this resource and also caused problems for future and present. Land use change is pointed out as affecting the recharging capacity in Upper Seonathbasin. The recharging ca-

capacity has decreased due to urbanization, hence natural recharge quantity are less in this areas which leads usually low water level depth for this region. Extensive use of groundwater in the Upper Seonath region started primarily for public water supply. But, at present, private usage of groundwater has become more significant, mostly by the industrial sector and agriculture in summer season is a cause of high drawdown in the study area and issue of low water table depth. From the results it can be concluded that in Upper Seonath catchment groundwater preservation by reasonable exploitation has to be employed and the use of groundwater abstraction rate at less than 500,000 m³/day were advised, so that the adverse impacts on ground water such as ground water contamination and drawdown of ground water level can be minimized. This study reveals a very valuable results for planner, manager and stakeholders to sustainable use of groundwater resources in Upper Seonath Basin.

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